

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some novel 4-substituted pyrazoline derivatives

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Abstract : A series of 5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles were synthesized by the reaction between 3-aryl-2-isobutanoyl-*N*-phenyl-acrylamide with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid as solvent gives acetyl pyrazoline. All the compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* biological assay like antibacterial activity towards Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains and antifungal activity towards *Aspergillus niger* at a concentration of 40 µg. The biological activities of synthesized compounds were compared with standard drugs.

Keywords : Pyrazolines, acetylpyrazolines, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Considerable interest has been focused on the pyrazoline structure, which has been known to possess a broad spectrum of biological activities such as tranquillizer, muscle relaxant, psychoanaleptic, anticonvulsant, antihypertensive and antidepressant¹⁻⁶. The discovery of this class of drugs provides an outstanding case history of modern drug development and also points out the unpredictability of biological activity from structural modification of a prototype drug molecule. Prodrug-based monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitors having hydrazide, hydrazine and amine moiety such as isocarboxazide⁷, phenelzine⁸ and meclobemide^{9,10} show prominent antidepressant activity in laboratory animals and human. Additionally, tranylcypromine like MAO inhibitors are mechanism based inactivators and they are metabolized by MAO with one electron of the nitrogen pair and to generate an imine, the other residing on a methylene carbon (R-C=NH₂⁺). The structures of the synthesised 2-pyrazoline derivatives are very similar to those of isocarboxazide. Earlier studies by Parmar *et al.*³ and Soni *et al.*⁴ demonstrated monoamine oxidase inhibitory activities of some pyrazolines and bicyclic pyrazolines in behavioral despair test¹¹⁻¹⁴. As part of our efforts in this area, a series of some new 5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-

pyrazoles and 1-acetyl-5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles have been synthesized and evaluated for their antimicrobial activities.

Condensation of different aryl aldehydes (2) with 4-methyl-3-oxo-*N*-phenylpentanamide (1) in presence of morpholine and acetic acid yielded corresponding 3-aryl-2-isobutanoyl-*N*-phenyl-acrylamide (3a-1) which on condensation with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid yielded 1-acetyl-5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles (4a-1) and further compounds 3a-1 on reaction with hydrazine hydrate give 5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles (5a-1).

The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned based on elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral data. All newly synthesized compounds have been screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity (Table 1).

Results and discussion

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method¹⁵ by measuring the zones of inhibition in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal screening results of compounds 4a-l and 5a-l

Compd.	R	Zones of inhibition in mm				
		Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity <i>A. niger</i>
		Gram-positive		Gram-negative		
		<i>B. coccus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Aerogenes</i>	<i>P. aeruginosu</i>	
4a	C ₆ H ₅ -	12	13	7	9	13
4b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	14	12	12	8	16
4c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	15	14	10	11	14
4d	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	12	14	11	9	18
4e	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	11	8	12	14	13
4f	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	10	7	11	10	11
4g	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	14	17	15	16	16
4h	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	12	18	19	14	18
4i	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	13	11	10	7	15
4j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	14	15	14	12	19
4k	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	12	13	15	16	17
4l	3-O-C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	13	11	9	8	18
5a	C ₆ H ₅ -	14	15	17	16	13
5b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	13	15	16	12	11
5c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	16	15	19	17	17
5d	4-F-C ₆ H ₄ -	18	14	16	13	9
5e	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	14	13	15	17	13
5f	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	11	12	13	15	19
5g	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	9	11	14	13	17
5h	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	16	12	17	18
5i	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	14	18	11	14	18
5j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	17	14	13	14	16
5k	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	18	12	15	13	17
5l	3-O-C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	15	16	11	12	17
Standard drugs	Amoxicillin	25	25	20	22	0
	Benzylpenicillin	18	19	21	21	0
	Ciprofloxacin	20	15	22	16	0
	Erythromycin	22	21	19	23	0
	Griseofulvin	0	0	0	0	26

bacterial strains such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus coccus* as well as Gram-negative bacterial strains such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Aerogenes* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* at 40 µg concentration. Standard drugs like Amoxicillin, Benzyl Penicillin, Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin and Griseofulvin were used for the comparison purpose (Table 1).

However the maximum activity was observed in compounds bearing R = *o*-chlorophenyl (4c), *p*-nitrophenyl (4j), *p*-fluorophenyl (5d), *m*-nitrophenyl (5k) substituents against *B. coccus*. The significant activity was observed in compounds bearing R = *p*-methoxyphenyl (4h), *p*-methylphenyl (4g), *m,p*-dimethoxyphenyl (5i), *p*-methoxyphenyl (5h) against *S. aureus*.

The maximum activity was displayed by the compounds bearing R = *p*-methoxyphenyl (4h), *p*-methylphenyl (4g), *o*-chlorophenyl (5c), phenyl (5a) against *Aerogenes*. In the case of *Pseudomonas* all the compounds were least active except R = *p*-methylphenyl (4g), *m*-nitrophenyl (4k), *o*-chlorophenyl (5c), *o*-hydroxyphenyl (5e).

The antifungal data revealed that compounds were least toxic to the fungal strain. However maximum activity was shown by the compounds bearing R = *p*-nitrophenyl (4j), *p*-methoxyphenyl (4h), *p*-hydroxy-*m*-methoxyphenyl (5f), *p*-methoxyphenyl (5h) against *A. niger*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates were used to access the reactions and purity of the synthesized compounds. All the products have been characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral study. IR spectra were recorded on

Shimadzu FTIR-8400 spectrophotometer in KBr disc and noteworthy absorption levels (cm⁻¹) are listed. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard, chemical shift in δ ppm. Mass spectra were determined using direct inlet probe on a GCMS-QP2010 mass spectrometer. Elemental analysis were performed on a Carlo Erba EA 1108 elemental analyzer.

General procedure for preparation of 3-aryl-2-isobutanoyl-N-phenyl-acrylamide (3a-l) :

A mixture of toluene, 4-methyl-3-oxo-*N*-phenyl-pentanamide (0.01 mol), different arylaldehydes (0.01 mol) and catalytic amount of morpholine in acetic acid was heated to the reflux temperature for 14–16 h. Water was removed from the reaction mixture by using Dean and Stark apparatus and then the mixture was cooled to room temperature, washed with sodium bisulphite solution and sodium bicarbonate solutions and finally with distilled water. The solvent was distilled out and the product was crystallised from hexane, which is sufficiently pure.

General procedure for preparation of 1-acetyl-5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[N-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazoles (4a-l) :

A mixture of 2-isobutanoyl-3-phenyl-*N*-phenyl-acrylamide (**3a-l**) (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was heated on water bath at 70 °C for 8 h and then cooled and poured into the crushed ice, filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from isopropyl alcohol. Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compounds are summarized as under.

(4a) 1-Acetyl-5-phenyl-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles : yield 41%; m.p. 220 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1380.8 (C(CH₃)₂), 1606.1 (C=C Ar), 1549.5 (C=N pyr), 1655.5 (C=O amide), 1690.6 (N-C=O), 3274.2 (N-H amide); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.12 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.22 (3H, s, CO-CH₃), 2.50 (1H, m, isopropyl), 3.99 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.44 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.10 (10H, aromatic), 10.42 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 72.16; H, 6.62; N, 12.04. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₃N₃O₂ (349.42) : C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03%).

(4b) 1-Acetyl-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 57%; m.p. 229 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1382.2 (C(CH₃)₂), 1601.0 (C=C Ar), 740.7 (C-Cl), 1547.4 (C=N pyr), 1652.2 (C=O amide), 1692.6 (N-C=O), 3275.3 (N-H amide); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.14 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.23 (3H, s, CO-CH₃), 2.55 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.12 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.64 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.32 (10H, aromatic), 10.32 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 65.70; H, 5.76; N, 10.97. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂ClN₃O₂ (383.87) : C, 65.71; H, 5.78; N, 10.95%).

(4c) 1-Acetyl-5-(*o*-chlorophenyl)-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 48%; m.p. 236 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1381.8 (C(CH₃)₂), 1609.0 (C=C Ar), 743.2 (C-Cl), 1546.9 (C=N pyr), 1651.2 (C=O amide), 1694.8 (N-C=O), 3277.0 (N-H amide); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.11 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.24 (3H, s, CO-CH₃), 2.50 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.19 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.64 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.30 (10H, aromatic), 10.33 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 65.76; H, 5.76; N, 10.97. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂ClN₃O₂ (383.87) : C, 65.71; H, 5.78; N, 10.95%).

(4d) 1-Acetyl-5-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-pyrazolines : yield 47%; m.p. 239 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1389.3 (C(CH₃)₂), 1600.6 (C=C Ar), 1091.7 (C-F), 1551.5 (C=N pyr), 1659.4 (C=O amide), 1691.1 (N-C=O), 3277.0 (N-H amide); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.09 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.18 (3H, s, CO-CH₃), 2.49 (1H, m, isopropyl), 3.97 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.38 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 6.92 (10H, aromatic), 10.22 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 68.64; H, 6.06; N, 11.47. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂FN₃O₂ (367.41) : C, 68.65; H, 6.04; N, 11.44%).

(4e) 1-Acetyl-5-(*p*-hydroxy-methoxy-phenyl)-3-isopropyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 41%; m.p. 222 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1381.2 (C(CH₃)₂), 1601.4 (C=C Ar), 1550.5 (C=N pyr), 1656.3 (C=O amide), 1692.4 (N-C=O), 3273.2 (N-H amide), 1211.9 (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.13 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.25 (3H, s, CO-CH₃), 3.25 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 2.53 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.12 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.64 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 6.90 (10H, aromatic), 10.50 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 66.81; H, 6.37; N, 10.61. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₃N₃O₃ (365.42) : C, 66.82; H, 6.37; N, 10.63%).

General procedure for preparation of 5-aryl-3-isopropyl-4-[N-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazoles (5a-l) :

A mixture of 2-isobutanoyl-3-phenyl-*N*-phenyl-acrylamide (**3a-l**) (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in methanol was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled and poured into the crushed ice, filtered, dried and recrystallized from isopropyl alcohol. Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compounds are summarized as under.

(5a) 3-Isopropyl-5-phenyl-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 56%; m.p. 169 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1387.8 (C(CH₃)₂), 1602.7 (C=C Ar), 1544.8 (C=N pyr), 3332.7 (N-H pyr), 1654.8 (C=O amide), 3296.1 (N-H amide); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.12 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.48 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.12 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.03 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.03–7.57 (10H, aromatic) (Found : C, 74.21; H, 6.85; N, 13.69. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁N₃O (307.59) : C, 74.24; H, 6.89; N, 13.67%).

(5b) 3-Isopropyl-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 57%;

m.p. 199 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1388.2 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1600.9 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ Ar), 1545.1 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ pyr), 3330.6 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ pyr), 1655.8 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide), 3299.1 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ amide), 744.5 ($\text{C}-\text{Cl}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 1.18 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.52 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.16 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.00 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.21 (9H, aromatic) (Found : C, 66.75; H, 5.91; N, 12.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$ (341.83) : C, 66.76; H, 5.90; N, 12.29%).

(5c) 3-Isopropyl-5-(*o*-chlorophenyl)-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 48%; m.p. 175 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1387.8 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1602.7 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ Ar), 1544.8 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ pyr), 1654.8 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide), 3296.1 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ amide), 735.5 ($\text{C}-\text{Cl}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 1.15 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.50 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.15 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.03 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 7.15 (9H, aromatic) (Found : C, 66.76; H, 5.92; N, 12.27. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$ (341.84) : C, 66.76; H, 5.90; N, 12.29%).

(5d) 3-Isopropyl-5-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 47%; m.p. 163 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1387.8 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1602.7 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ Ar), 1544.8 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ pyr), 3332.7 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ pyr), 1654.8 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide), 3296.1 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ amide), 1095.7 ($\text{C}-\text{F}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 1.14 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.54 (1H, m, isopropyl), 4.11 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.07 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 6.98 (9H, aromatic) (Found : C, 70.15; H, 6.21; N, 12.91. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{FN}_3\text{O}$ (325.38) : C, 70.13; H, 6.20; N, 12.91%).

(5e) 3-Isopropyl-5-(*p*-hydroxy-methoxy-phenyl)-4-[*N*-phenyl-aminocarbonyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole : yield 32%; m.p. 210 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 1387.8 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1602.7 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ Ar), 1544.8 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ pyr), 3332.7 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ pyr), 1654.8 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide), 3296.1 ($\text{N}-\text{H}$ amide), 1210.6 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 1.08 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.40 (1H, m, isopropyl), 3.15 (3H s, CH_3), 4.10 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 5.03 (1H, d, pyrazoline), 6.8 (8H, aromatic)

(Found : C, 67.99; H, 6.55; N, 11.88. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ (353.41) : C, 67.97; H, 6.56; N, 11.89%).

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